

Comparative Study of Peak Expiratory Flow Rate among Power Loom Workers In Relation To Gender Distribution in Rural Area in Salem District

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Abstract:

Introduction: Occupational exposure in power loom industries is a known risk for respiratory diseases. This study aimed to compare Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) between male and female power loom workers and assess the impact of gender, years of exposure, and workplace conditions on respiratory function.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 250 power loom workers from rural Salem, Tamil Nadu. Demographic, socioeconomic, and occupational data were collected via a structured questionnaire. PEFR was assessed using Wright's Peak Flow Meter, and statistical analysis compared PEFR values by gender and exposure duration.

Results and Discussion: Significant gender differences in PEFR were observed, with males consistently showing higher PEFR values compared to females. In the 16–20 years exposure category, males predominated in the higher PEFR ranges (351–400 lpm, 401–450 lpm), while females were primarily in the lower ranges (251–300 lpm, 351–400 lpm). As exposure duration increased, PEFR values declined in both genders, with the most significant decline observed in females, highlighting the cumulative effects of prolonged exposure. The findings emphasize the compounded respiratory health risks for females due to dual exposure, and the overall decline in lung function over time for both genders.

Conclusion: This study highlights significant gender-based differences in PEFR among power loom workers. Implementing preventive measures like improved ventilation, use of protective equipment, and regular health monitoring can help mitigate respiratory health risks in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: Power loom workers, Peak Expiratory flow rate, Respiratory Health, Pulmonary function test, Occupational hazards.

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Introduction

Occupation not only serves as a source of livelihood but also represents a significant part of an individual's daily life, with nearly one-third of a lifetime spent in the workplace. Occupational environments, particularly those involving exposure to pollutants, can significantly affect respiratory health. Among such occupations, power loom work is particularly hazardous due to the constant inhalation of cotton dust and airborne pollutants generated during the textile manufacturing process. Dust from cotton and other materials poses severe respiratory hazards, with health outcomes closely tied to the type, duration, and level of exposure to such airborne pollutants. [1] Globally, approximately 40% of workers in dusty textile environments suf-

fer from dust-related diseases. Occupational pulmonary diseases, such as asbestosis and silicosis, are particularly widespread and debilitating, influenced by the size, concentration, and persistence of airborne particles. Environmental factors, particularly occupational exposure, play a critical role in the onset and progression of respiratory morbidities like asthma and rhinitis. [2] This occupational setting is compounded by gender-related physiological and socio-environmental factors. These issues are exacerbated by the cumulative impact of workplace and domestic exposures, particularly among women in rural areas, who may also be exposed to indoor air pollution from biomass fuels during cooking. Power loom workers, due to prolonged

exposure to hazardous environments, exhibit a higher prevalence of both obstructive and restrictive lung function abnormalities, highlighting the need for focused research on their respiratory health. Understanding gender differences in PEFR among power loom workers can shed light on occupational hazards and inform interventions to mitigate risks. [3]

Pulmonary Function Tests (PFTs) provide a reliable, objective, and quantifiable method to assess lung function which depend on the integrity of the airways, pulmonary vascular system alveolar septa, respiratory muscles and respiratory control mechanisms. PFTs offer a standardized and objective means to assess the presence and severity of respiratory dysfunctions. They are crucial for the early detection of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and the evaluation of occupational lung diseases. Among PFTs, the Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) is a widely used, simple, and effective screening tool for detecting obstructive lung conditions. PEFR, measured using Wright's peak flow meter, reflects the maximum rate of air expelled during a forced expiration. [4] In the Indian context, young males typically exhibit PEFR values ranging between 450–550 liters per minute, while females demonstrate slightly lower values of 320–470 liters per minute, attributed to physiological differences. [5] This study investigates the PEFR among power loom workers in rural Salem, comparing values between males and females to explore gender-specific occupational health risks. It aims to provide actionable insights into the respiratory health challenges faced by this vulnerable population and guide preventive interventions.

Materials and Methods

This study included 250 power loom workers from rural Salem district of Tamil Nadu. Participants were selected based on inclusion criteria, which included workers aged 30–70 years without known respiratory illnesses. Exclusion criteria ruled out individuals with a history of smoking, pre-existing respiratory conditions, or those outside the specified age range. Written informed consent was obtained, and ethical clearance from the institution was secured before the commencement of the study (Ref. No. IEC/11/94). Data collection included demographic, socioeconomic, and occupational variables. The demographic parameters recorded included age, education level, family type, marital status and residence type. Occupational parameters included work duration in power loom industries and workplace conditions. These variables were

collected using a structured questionnaire, providing a comprehensive profile for analyzing the impact of demographic, socioeconomic, and occupational factors on respiratory health in this population.

Data analysis focused on comparing gender differences in Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) with various other factors, such as years of exposure, workplace conditions, and other demographic and occupational variables. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, and inferential statistics, including independent t-tests and one-way ANOVA, were applied to compare PEFR between males and females across different categories of work duration, workplace conditions, and other variables. This comprehensive approach enabled a detailed understanding of how PEFR varies by gender in relation to exposure duration, workplace conditions, and other demographic and occupational factors.

Results

The study included a total of 250 participants, comprising 153 males and 97 females. The age distribution revealed that the largest group was aged 51–60 years, with 61 males and 28 females, accounting for 89 participants in total. This was followed by the 41–50 years age group with 61 participants (35 males and 26 females). Participants aged over 60 years included 31 males and 26 females, while those aged 30–40 years constituted the smallest group, with 26 males and 17 females. In terms of education level, secondary education was the most common, reported by 85 participants (61 males and 24 females). Primary education was completed by 91 participants (48 males and 43 females), while 29 participants (13 males and 16 females) reported having no formal education. Higher secondary education was completed by 33 participants (22 males and 11 females), and 12 participants (9 males and 3 females) were graduates. The majority of participants were married, with 191 individuals (107 males and 84 females), while 59 participants (46 males and 13 females) were unmarried. Regarding family type, 131 participants (88 males and 43 females) lived in nuclear families, while 119 participants (65 males and 54 females) were from joint families. Residence type showed that most participants, 146 in total (97 males and 49 females), were from rural areas, followed by 71 participants (34 males and 37 females) from semi-urban areas. A smaller group of 33 participants (22 males and 11 females) resided in urban areas. [Table No.1]

Table 1: Socio - Demographic Details of Study Participants

Details		Male	Female	Total
Age	30-40 Years	26	17	43
	41 - 50 Years	35	26	61
	51 - 60 Years	61	28	89
	>60 Years	31	26	57
Education Level	No education	13	16	29
	Primary	48	43	91
	Secondary	61	24	85
	Higher Secondary	22	11	33
	Graduate	9	3	12
Marital status	Married	107	84	191
	Unmarried	46	13	59
Family Type	Nuclear	88	43	131
	Joint	65	54	119
Residence Type	Rural	97	49	146
	Semi Urban	34	37	71
	Urban	22	11	33

The study examined years of occupational exposure among 250 power loom workers, including 153 males and 97 females. For workers with 10–15 years of exposure, there were 31 males and 16 females, while in the 16–20 years category, 38 males and 24 females were represented. In the 21–25 years group, there were 24 males and 14 fe-

males, and in the 26–30 years category, 32 males and 13 females. Among those with 31–35 years of exposure, there were 8 males and 7 females, while the 36–40 years group comprised 9 males and 10 females. Lastly, for workers with more than 40 years of exposure, there were 11 males and 13 females.[Chart No.1]

Chart 1: Gender-wise Distribution of Power Loom Workers Based on Years of Exposure

The study assessed Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) among male and female powerloom workers across different years of exposure categories [Table No.2].

Among males with 10–15 years of exposure, the majority had PEFR in the range of 351–400 lpm (13 workers), followed by 251–300 lpm (4 workers), while only 2 workers each were in the <250 and 301–350 lpm categories.

In the higher PEFR ranges, 4 workers had 401–

450 lpm, and none had >450 lpm. For those with 16–20 years of exposure, most workers had PEFR in the 351–400 lpm range (15 workers), followed by 401–450 lpm (10 workers) and >450 lpm (6 workers). In the 21–25 years exposure category, 9 workers were in the 251–300 lpm group, while 5 workers each fell into the 301–350 lpm, 351–400 lpm, and 401–450 lpm ranges, with only 1 worker in the >450 lpm range.

Workers with 26–30 years of exposure were

similarly distributed, with 9 in the 251–300 lpm group, 5 in 351–400 lpm, 4 in 301–350 lpm, and fewer in other ranges.

Among females with 10–15 years of exposure, the highest numbers were in the 351–400 lpm category (8 workers), followed by 251–300 lpm (5 workers) and <250 lpm (3 workers), with a small representation in the >450 lpm range (1 worker). For 16–20 years of exposure, the majority were in the

351–400 lpm category (6 workers), followed by 251–300 lpm (4 workers). In the 21–25 years category, most females had PEFR in the 351–400 lpm range (3 workers), while fewer were distributed across other categories.

Similarly, for 26–30 years of exposure, most females were in the 251–300 lpm range (9 workers), followed by 351–400 lpm (6 workers). [Chart No.2]

Table 2: Distribution of PEFR by Years of Exposure and Gender

Years of Exposure	Males						Females					
	PEFR						PEFR					
	< 250	251 - 300	301 - 350	351 - 400	401 - 450	>450	< 250	251 - 300	301 - 350	351 - 400	401 - 450	> 450
10 - 15	2	4	2	13	4	0	3	5	4	8	1	1
16 - 20	2	4	5	15	10	6	3	4	4	6	2	1
21 - 25	1	9	5	5	5	1	3	2	3	3	1	0
26 - 30	2	9	4	5	3	1	1	9	4	6	1	0
31 - 35	1	1	2	4	2	0	0	2	1	2	0	0
36 - 40	4	2	1	3	1	0	2	4	0	2	0	0
>40	3	4	1	2	4	1	2	5	0	1	1	0
Total	15	33	20	47	29	9	14	31	16	28	6	2

Chart 2: Comparison between PEFR and Gender in Powerloom Workers

Discussion

Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) is a widely used, simple, and reliable measure of ventilatory function that reflects the maximum rate of airflow during forced expiration after maximal inspiration. It is an essential tool for assessing respiratory health and monitoring obstructive lung diseases, particularly in occupational settings. The present study examined PEFR among male and female powerloom workers across varying durations of occupational exposure, revealing significant gender differences and other critical observations.

The present study highlights significant gender

variations and critical observations regarding Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) among powerloom workers with varying years of occupational exposure. Males consistently demonstrated higher PEFR values than females across all exposure categories, with a greater proportion achieving higher ranges, such as 401–450 lpm and >450 lpm, particularly in the 16–20 years exposure category. This disparity is largely attributed to the physiological advantage of stronger chest muscles in males. However, females showed lower PEFR values due to dual exposure from occupational hazards and indoor air pollution caused by cooking with traditional fuels like wood, cow dung, and kerosene. This chronic

exposure to pollutants likely exacerbated respiratory stress in females, leading to irritation and narrowing of the airways. Workers with shorter exposure durations (10–15 years) exhibited better PEFR values overall, with males predominantly falling in higher PEFR ranges. As exposure duration increased, a gradual decline in PEFR was observed in both genders, with a pronounced drop in the >40 years exposure category, where most participants had PEFR values in the <250 lpm and 251–300 lpm ranges. This suggests that prolonged exposure to occupational pollutants like cotton dust significantly impacts respiratory function over time. Interestingly, females in shorter exposure categories showed slightly better PEFR distributions compared to those with longer exposure, indicating that cumulative exposure disproportionately affects female respiratory health.

Poor workplace conditions, particularly in congested and poorly ventilated environments, further exacerbated the decline in PEFR across all exposure groups, emphasizing the critical role of adequate ventilation in mitigating occupational hazards. Socioeconomic factors, such as education, housing type, and residence, also influenced PEFR, with workers in kutchra or semi-pucca houses and rural areas demonstrating lower PEFR values, likely due to higher exposure to pollutants and limited access to healthcare.

The findings of this study align with previous research highlighting the adverse effects of occupational cotton dust exposure on respiratory health. Reduced Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR) observed among power loom workers in this study parallels the results of Derso Y et al., who reported significantly reduced pulmonary function parameters, including Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), FEV1, and PEFR, among cotton-ginning workers compared to controls. [6] Derso et al. also noted a high prevalence of respiratory symptoms (68.6%) among cotton-ginning workers, with contributing factors such as female gender, lower education levels, specific workplace roles, and the lack of personal protective equipment (PPE). These findings resonate with our study, where poor workplace conditions and inadequate protective measures likely contributed to the observed decline in PEFR, particularly among females who face dual exposure to occupational and domestic pollutants.

Similarly, Saoji et al. highlighted a significant relationship between lung function impairment and exposure duration in spinning mill workers, compounded by smoking behavior. [7] While this study excluded smokers to eliminate confounding effects, the progressive decline in PEFR with increased years of exposure observed among both males and females supports the impact of prolonged occupational exposure on lung function. The findings from Saoji et al. reinforce the need to account for

cumulative exposure and workplace environment as critical determinants of respiratory health. Ahmad A et al. emphasized that respiratory morbidities are closely linked to workplace conditions and duration of exposure. [8] Our study corroborates this observation, showing that poorly ventilated and congested environments significantly contribute to reduce PEFR among power loom workers. Furthermore, females demonstrated a more pronounced decline in PEFR over time, likely exacerbated by their dual burden of occupational and domestic pollutant exposure, as highlighted in our findings and supported by Derso et al.

The combined analysis of gender and exposure duration revealed that while males generally maintained higher PEFR values, the impact of prolonged exposure was more linear in males and more pronounced in females, suggesting that chronic exposure compounded by domestic pollutant exposure significantly affects female respiratory health. These findings underscore the importance of targeted interventions, including improving workplace ventilation, providing personal protective equipment, promoting cleaner cooking fuels, and implementing regular pulmonary function testing and awareness programs. Such measures can reduce the dual burden of occupational and domestic exposure, improve PEFR values, and enhance the quality of life for both male and female power loom workers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the respiratory health hazards of cotton exposure among male and female power loom workers, emphasizing the gender differences in PEFR values. To mitigate the risk of occupational diseases, preventive measures such as reducing exposure through shift work, improving workplace ventilation, using masks during working hours, and conducting routine physical examinations annually are essential. Additionally, females should be encouraged to strengthen their respiratory muscles through exercises or yoga to improve lung function and reduce the impact of prolonged exposure.

References

1. Nafees AA, Fatmi Z, Kadir MM, Sathiakumar N. Pattern and predictors for respiratory illnesses and symptoms and lung function among textile workers in Karachi, Pakistan. *Occup Environ Med.* 2013 Feb; 70(2):99-107. doi: 10.1136/oemed-2011-100561. Epub 2012 Nov 15. PMID: 23155188.
2. Mansouri F, Pili JP, Abbasi A, Soltani M, Izadi N. Respiratory problems among cotton textile workers. *Lung India.* 2016 Mar-Apr; 33(2):163-6. doi: 10.4103/0970-2113.177444. PMID: 27051104; PMCID: PMC4797435.
3. Kobayashi H, Kanoh S, Motoyoshi K, Aida S.

- Diffuse lung disease caused by cotton fibre inhalation but distinct from byssinosis. *Thorax*. 2004 Dec; 59(12):1095-7. doi: 10.1136/thx.2003.014027. PMID: 15563711; PMCID: PMC1746888.
4. Wright BM. A miniature Wright peak-flow meter. *Br Med J*. 1978 Dec 9; 2(6152):1627-8. doi: 10.1136/bmj.2.6152.1627. PMID: 728756; PMCID: PMC1608889.
 5. Ray D, Rajaratnam A, Richard J. Peak expiratory flow in rural residents of Tamil Nadu, India. *Thorax*. 1993 Feb; 48(2):163-6. doi: 10.1136/thx.48.2.163. PMID: 8493632; PMCID: PMC464296.
 6. Derso Y, Dagneb B, Akalu Y, Getu AA, Getnet M, Yeshaw Y. Pulmonary function, respiratory symptoms and associated factors among cotton-ginning workers at Gondar city, Northwest Ethiopia: a comparative cross-sectional study. *Int J Physiol Pathophysiol Pharmacol*. 2021 Oct 15; 13(5):140-147. PMID: 34868464; PMCID: PMC8611241.
 7. Ajeet Saoji. A Cross-Sectional Study of Effect of Smoking on Lung Functions of Spinning Mill Workers. *The Anthropologist* [Internet]. 2012 [cited 2024 Sept. 02]; 14(1):57-60. Available from: https://www.academia.edu/98545570/A_Cross_Sectional_Study_of_Effect_of_Smoking_on_Lung_Functions_of_Spinnig_Mill_Workers
 8. Ahmad A. Morbidity Profile and Associated risk factors among Power-loom Weavers in Mau district in Uttar Pradesh. *International journal of social sciences*. 2023 Mar 25; 12(1).